

Social Marketing in Turkey

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ABSTRACT

Marketing is an omnipresent phenomena in many facets of our life. To get success in our life, the promotion procedure dictates marketing. We use marketing strategies to encourage people to demonstrate excellent actions throughout society. The objectives and initiatives of civil society groups or foundations shape social marketing. The notion of social marketing, introduced to our nation in the 1980s, has been executed by many groups until the present day. This course will provide a comprehensive introduction to social marketing. The elements of social marketing that differentiate it from conventional and social marketing will be elucidated. Instances of research undertaken in our nation will be referenced.

Keywords: *Marketing, Social Marketing, Community Marketing, Social Marketing in Turkey*

INTRODUCTION

Certain actions are created and executed to instill a societal concept among a designated target population. The fundamental aims of marketing include product planning, price, selling, distribution, market research, and communication. It encompasses the outlined goals in social marketing. Consequently, non-profit products and services are included inside marketing. Marketing tactics and technologies are used in social marketing to engage a particular target demographic. In addition to its significance in commercial entities, marketing plays a crucial role in non-profit organizations, workplaces, places of worship, public service institutions, and volunteer groups. The concept of particular enterprises assuming diverse responsibilities in addressing social issues has grown progressively. In the next years, it is anticipated that hunger, violence, and illnesses such as AIDS would be addressed. Issues such as these disrupt societal harmony. Consequently, civil society groups and foundations play crucial roles in addressing socioeconomic issues. To incorporate diverse ideas and perspectives into society and effectuate substantial changes in certain thinking and behavior patterns, societal campaigns must be implemented.

To define social marketing, one must consider the perspectives of several professionals. The foundations of social marketing were established by the research of scholars such Wiebe,

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Mendelsohn, Lazarsfeld, Merton, Hyman, and Sheatsley throughout the 1940s and 1950s, focusing on public relations, advertising, communication, and social psychology (Rotshild, 1997, 308). Kotler and Andreasen describe social marketing as the pursuit of fostering social behaviors not for personal profit, but for the collective benefit of society and the populace at large (Weinreich, 1999).

For the past 30 years, research on social marketing has been undertaken in the health sector, focusing on public awareness regarding cardiovascular health, the formulation of nutritional policies to combat obesity, initiatives against smoking, efforts to address viruses such as AIDS/HIV, the societal integration of substance-using youth, environmental protection, the education of refugee children, and the employment of women. In this paper, I will define social marketing and elucidate the notion via my analyses of studies completed and my overall assessments of research in Turkey. I shall specify the research undertaken in Turkey involving corporations and selected civil society groups.

PURPOSE AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study aims to highlight the significance of marketing and the impact of marketing tactics on various research, particularly in the context of social marketing and related studies undertaken in Turkey.

1. SOCIAL MARKETING

Social marketing is an initiative designed to effect social change. Effective social campaigns need the use of marketing tactics (Bayraktaroğlu and İlter, 2007). Moreover, in social marketing, societal interests and social purpose take precedence over economic motives (Bayraktaroğlu and İlter, 2007). Environmental cleanup requires marketing to affect individual behavior (Bayraktaroğlu and İlter, 2007). Additional challenges emerged from social marketing, including females' education and the promotion of economic growth in rural regions. The success rate will be elevated if analogous initiatives are executed using comparable

methodologies for a particular product in social marketing aimed at commercial objectives (Bayraktaroğlu and İlter, 2007).

1.1. Factors Affecting the Appearance of the Term Social Marketing in Literature

The belief that companies instigate societal issues persists in contemporary discourse (Torlak, 2022). Companies endeavor to address social issues using a fraction of their profits (Torlak, 2022). Consequently, the anticipation of beneficial impacts on business and brand perceptions is vital in guiding choices about the implementation of social marketing initiatives (Torlak, 2022). The concept that ideas, cultures, artistic works, political ideologies, and social welfare concerns may be directed towards specific audiences via marketing has evolved, leading to the significant emergence of the phrase social marketing in marketing literature (Torlak, 2022). Contemporary business challenges include exorbitant pricing resulting from monopolistic practices, income inequality, restricted access to certain products and services for specific demographics, consumer deception through the promotion of health-detrimental products for profit maximization, the safeguarding of marginalized groups, and the manipulation of children via advertising (Torlak, 2022). The dissemination of news on these and analogous topics via mass media has heightened societal awareness (Torlak, 2022).

Adverse business news perceived by the public, the inefficacy of governmental administrations in addressing social issues, and escalating disparities have prompted research focused on resolving social problems (Torlak, 2022). Customer expectations of firms have escalated daily (Torlak, 2022).

Alongside enhancing public awareness and bolstering support, companies seek to fortify their image via the principle of social marketing directed at customers (Torlak, 2022). Consequently, several enterprises have aided in addressing issues such as health, education, and hunger at local, regional, national, and worldwide levels via social marketing initiatives (Torlak, 2022). Social marketing strategies contribute to addressing social issues, effectively communicate these issues to relevant target groups, enhance awareness, and bolster the brand image of firms (Torlak, 2022). This scenario illustrates that a social concept is disseminated via social

marketing, effectively communicating non-profit products and services to target audiences, thereby enhancing the business's image and reputation in relation to addressing social issues (Torlak, 2022).

1.2. General Evaluation on Social Marketing

The idea of social marketing is less prevalent in marketing and national applications compared to the notion of social responsibility (Torlak, 2022). Theoretically, the notion that marketing is inapplicable non a social setting is one of the explanations (Torlak, 2022). Adopting an alternative viewpoint reveals that the idea may convey erroneous or divergent meanings to organizations or their target audiences, hence presenting a distinct issue (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.126). The marketing initiative of a social phenomenon exemplifies this notion (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.126). This notion raises the question of its ethical implications (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.126). Furthermore, although social marketing employs similar scientific methods as conventional marketing, it exhibits distinct characteristics (Bayraktaroğlu and İlter, 2007). Certain issues absent in conventional marketing are seen in social marketing (Bayraktaroğlu and İlter, 2007). The execution of social marketing initiatives is more challenging than that of conventional marketing efforts due to the complexities involved in altering certain habits amongst constrained possibilities (Bayraktaroğlu and İlter, 2007). Consequently, success in social marketing is attained by acknowledging potential challenges and implementing preventive measures (Bayraktaroğlu and İlter, 2007).

1.3. Differences Between Community Marketing and Social Marketing

Social marketing entails the socially conscious and responsible delivery of products and services to consumers by a commercial entity, aligned with their requirements (Torlak, 2022). Consequently, it represents a distinct notion from social marketing (Torlak, 2022). Social marketing encompasses social and responsibility concepts into commercial marketing strategies (Torlak, 2022). Commercial marketing employs ideas, tactics, and instruments pertaining to

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social concerns (Torlak, 2022). Although social marketing prioritizes the client, it is fundamentally directed towards the corporation and its supply chain (Torlak, 2022).

2. HISTORY OF THE CONCEPT OF SOCIAL MARKETING AND ITS INTRODUCTION TO TURKEY

The notion of marketing was introduced in our nation in 1957 with the publication of "Marketing Principles and Turkey Practice" by Dr. Mehmet Oruç, Associate Professor of Business Economics at the Faculty of Economics (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p. 126). A market, a designated market customer, and an entity that supplies items or services to the designated market must exist (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.126). Therefore, marketing is seen as a commercial or retail role. This notion reflects a viewpoint that is pertinent in the first phases of marketing but progressively wanes and is mostly erroneous in contemporary contexts (Kurtoğlu;2007, p.126). The concept of marketing has evolved through many phases, characterized by the changing priorities of firms (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.126). This cycle, beginning with the designation of product management, progressing to sales management, and culminating in marketing, is fundamentally influenced by the prominence given to consumer and societal benefits (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p. 126). Prior to the 1980s in Turkey, manufacturing posed a greater challenge than marketing (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.126). Prior to 1980, firms were unable to formulate marketing plans owing to supply shortages and import challenges stemming from foreign currency issues (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.126). The application and planning process of the creation, pricing, distribution, and promotion of goods, services, and strategies designed to fulfill requirements and achieve company objectives is termed marketing (Mucuk, 1999; 5).

The formulation of strategies and concepts within the definition delineates social marketing (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). Product purchasers possess values (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). The definition of the product is unrestricted. The product encompasses not just a specific drug but also all elements that induce change while fulfilling an individual's need (Cemalcılar, 1999; p.81). The concept, value, or strategy is also included into the product specification (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). The product's capacity to effect change is also significant. Several critical elements are considered while formulating a marketing strategy about the representation of a

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product or value. The product's attributes, value, provenance, and social status are considered. The price might convey information to the customer. The pricing-based marketing strategy is executed via the proportionate positioning of the price (Sirgy, 1998; 74). The pricing rate is established based on the product or target demographic (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). This approach involves economic and psychological variables in marketing (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). Location and distribution are critical components of marketing (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). The frequency of client exposure to the product is significant, since it facilitates memorization of the product (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). The product's distribution location and the distributor's operational procedures are also crucial in marketing (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). Promotion and communication are essential components of marketing (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). The communication phenomena facilitates the convergence of institutions and consumers (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). The marketing idea is a managerial philosophy focused on the execution of an organization's operations (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.127). The contributions of the company outside marketing are as significant. Marketing may also influence the socio-economic aspects of individuals (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128). Moreover, some marketing campaigns occur in various places at distinct periods (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128). The notion of social marketing was introduced in Turkey later than in the West (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128).

2.1. Relationship between Social Responsibility and Social Marketing

Social responsibility is a notion that enhances the long-term image of a business without pursuing profit, hence elevating the social consciousness of specific entities (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128). It constitutes an indivisible entity with social marketing. Some analysts assert that it is synonymous with social marketing (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128). The research lacks agreement about the intrinsic connection between social responsibility and marketing (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128). Fox and Kotler said that the notions of social marketing and social responsibility inside non-governmental organizations are distinct (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128). There is a lack of agreement about the implementation of social marketing concepts inside the private sector (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128). Kotler, Roberto, and Lee assert that social marketing aligns with the objectives of the commercial sector (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128). In contrast to their views, Karim,

Rangun, and Again assert that social marketing and the commercial sector are distinct entities (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128). According to their perspective, social responsibility is a subordinate objective of corporations (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.128).

Scholars such W. Lazar, Kotler, and Levy have presented their concepts about social responsibility and social marketing. Lazar said that marketing strategies may be used to address social issues. Kotler and Levy asserted that marketing approaches are applicable to non-governmental groups as well.

At times, the concepts of social responsibility and social marketing were indistinguishable (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.129). Kotler and Kelley discussed social marketing and its concepts in their book 'Social Marketing Perspectives and Views'. In the 1980s and 1990s, several experts and scholars adopted a 'program emphasis' approach rather than an institutional focus (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.129). This concept aimed to influence behavior and posited that marketing would provide a robust technical infrastructure for fostering socially desirable behaviors (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.129). This novel perspective serves as the impetus for the social marketing project (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.129).

2.2. Social Marketing in Turkey

The social marketing technique emerged prominently in Turkey after the 1980s (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.129). The social marketing technique originated from instances of social advertising in our nation (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.129). This methodology was subsequently extended via social campaigns (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.129). The instructional advertising produced by toothpaste firms in 1984 and thereafter were the first endeavors in social marketing (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.129). To enhance knowledge of first aid in our nation, Halk Yaşam Sigorta A.Ş. and the Emergency Medicine Association conducted social marketing initiatives under the 'First Step for First Aid' campaign (Sezer, 1999, p.60). The campaign started on December 4, 1997, and concluded in June 1998 (Sezer, 1999, p.60). First aid constitutes the first action prior to medical assistance. The objective of first aid is to avert further deterioration of the patient's condition or to avoid mortality. The Emergency Medicine Association has received significant public engagement

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about this project (Sezer, 1999, p.60). A multitude of individuals who contacted them by completing the 'First Aid Volunteer' coupon in the press releases were educated via seminars and informational booklets (Sezer, 1999, p.60). The essential measures to be implemented in the event of an accident were elucidated via instructional videos produced by the association's member physicians (Sezer, 1999, p.60).

Messages executed in the campaign:

- The public should be educated on first aid practices and people who do not have first aid training should never intervene in the sick or injured.
- Call an ambulance immediately
- The necessary initiatives should be carried out correctly and on time.

The scope of training activities includes examples such as electric shock, poisoning, burns, drowning, falling injuries, heart attacks and traffic accidents (Sezer, 1999, p.60).

Activities implemented in the campaign:

- A press conference was held on December 4, 1997.
- First Aid Week was celebrated between 4-10 December.
- Advertisements containing First Aid Volunteer coupons have been published.
- A free phone line has been established at 0 800 211 42 00, which can be reached by those who want to become First Aid Volunteers.
- www.ilkyardim.org address, which includes basic first aid information, has been opened for use.

Applications from more than 10,000 people who wanted to be first aid volunteers were evaluated in the next stage (Sezer, 1999, p.61).

- 1000 people attended the General Evaluation part of the first aid training that started in January, and almost 170 people attended the Basic Life Support course held in March.
- First aid tags were addressed in February. Tags containing information such as blood type, allergies and phone numbers of relatives that should be applied by Healthcare Workers in emergency situations were distributed on February 14, Valentine's Day.

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- The issue of first aid kits was brought to the agenda in March, and they were distributed free of charge to those who participated in the campaign.
- It was stated that ambulances should be given way in April and a first aid map showing the locations of health institutions providing emergency care was implemented.

The 'Aygaz Warns Against Home Accidents' Campaign exemplifies social marketing. This campaign was conducted under the guidance of Prof. Dr. Ömer Türel, a faculty member in the Department of First and Emergency Aid at Istanbul Medical Faculty (Sezer, 1999, p.61). Domestic accidents inflict injury on individuals comparable to that of vehicular accidents (Sezer, 1999, p.61). Burns, scalds, falls, fractures, water heater incidents, cuts, and injuries are among the potential hazards (Sezer, 1999, p.61). The campaign aims to address public misconceptions about home accidents, outline preventive measures, and specify necessary safeguards (Sezer, 1999, p.61).

Steps followed in the campaign:

- It was planned to be implemented between 28 March and 31 December 1998.
- More than 1200 dealers were informed about the campaign.
- 1250 dealer vehicles published messages to increase the effectiveness of the campaign between March 21 and April 31.
- Leaflets containing warnings about five types of accidents were distributed.
- www.evkazalari.org website has been opened for internet users.
- Campaign files were sent to the Ministry of Health and various public institutions.
- The press conference was held on March 23, 1998.
- The TV movies directed by Haldun Dormen were broadcast between March 28 and May 31.
- Five separate spots containing the messages of the films were broadcast on national radio channels.
- Home Accidents: The Danger Next Door, Brainstorming. In May 1998, in cooperation with the White Point Foundation, with the mentorship of Tinaz Titiz, a participatory problem-solving meeting and brainstorming session were held, and the opinions of individuals from sectors such as industrial designers, home appliance and household

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goods manufacturers, users, emergency service personnel, insurance companies were discussed to discuss measures that could be taken to reduce home accidents.

- Collaborations were made with Public Education Centers to raise awareness among housewives.
- Printed materials, films and meeting notes were shared in the education departments of non-governmental organizations such as the Turkish Education Volunteers Foundation and Support for Contemporary Life.

However, social marketing is different from social advertising or social communication (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.129). In general, in order to provide social development for the benefit of society, campaigns first developed as social advertising and then as social communication and began to evolve into social marketing, and instead of just promotion, all marketing mix elements and marketing research were applied together (Kurtoğlu; 2007, p.129).

3. SUGGESTIONS THAT MAY MAKE SOCIAL MARKETING EFFECTIVE

These are the main factors for successful social marketing (Wiebe, 1952):

- Evaluations on the subject should be obtained from the target audience;
- Directing the target audience to demonstrate certain behaviors (such as TEV's "contribute to education" example)
- Establishing mechanisms that will allow individuals to achieve their goals (sharing account numbers with those who want to contribute or the foundation's phone number with those who will support a campaign)
- Ensuring the effectiveness and adequacy of the mechanisms in fulfilling their responsibilities (processes such as where and when flowers will be sent via the customer's phone and receiving the money at the place and time specified by the customer and delivering the receipt, if requested, without any disruptions or difficulties)
- Reducing costs regarding transactions to be carried out by the customer (customers can easily reach TEV branches.)

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In addition, environmental factors, the person's ability and image affect the behavioral change of the target audience (Andreasen, 1997; Fishbein et al.).

4. CONCLUSION

The fundamental components of marketing are price, planning, distribution, sales, communication, and market research of the product. Conventional marketing strategies are also used in social marketing. The objective of social marketing is to enhance social awareness. Civil Society Organizations are the primary agents of social and social marketing. Facilitating significant behavioral modifications regarding sensitivity and guiding individuals towards exemplary and healthy practices are the elements of social and social marketing.

For social marketing to succeed, it is essential to identify the target audience and influence their behavior. An appropriate distribution channel is essential for effective social marketing. Cost reduction is a crucial element in attaining the desired behavior. Marketing research, product promotion, and the use of mass media to engage the target audience need specialized communication tools, divisions of the firm or civil society organization in diverse locations, and volunteer personnel.

Social marketing began in our nation throughout the 1980s via corporations and has persisted to the present day via the endeavors of associations since the 1990s. The Foundation for Children with Leukemia, established in 1998 with a modest office, has significantly contributed to improving treatment outcomes via efforts focused on leukemia in select locations around Turkey. The foundation's activities have heightened awareness of the condition and improved the trust index in our nation by positively impacting the academic and social lives of children affected by this illness, as well as their treatment procedures. The primary component contributing to the attained success is the phenomena of social marketing.

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